

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D9.1

Principles for impact assessment of
PILOTING against SoEL
requirements

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI HLEG	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
AV	Autonomous Vehicle
CFR	Chapter of the Fundamental Rights
CMR	Carriage of Goods by Road
CoE	Council of Europe
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IA	Impact Assessment
IR	Infrared camera
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
SoEL	Social, Ethical and legal
SORA	Specific Operation Risk Assessment
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicles
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
VLOS	Visual line of sight
WP	Work package

Table 1. Acronyms list

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable constitutes the first deliverable of work package WP9, which concerns the PILOTING project's social, ethical, and legal (SoEL) aspects. The role of this deliverable is to identify, in broad terms, the legal and ethical principles which will apply to the PILOTING project. The identification of these principles and the relevant legal frameworks will allow defining a set of requirements that will constitute a benchmark against which project activities and outcomes will be assessed, the "PILOTING Impact Assessment Framework".

The "PILOTING Impact Assessment Framework" will be defined taking into account the different PILOTING Uses Cases. In order to set guidelines for the impact assessment which apply among different types of pilots and geographical/legal implications, the PILOTING Uses Cases have been classified according to the type of infrastructure (refineries, bridges/viaducts or tunnels) and the type of robotic solution (UAV, UGV, crawler) employed, obtaining six "PILOTING Impact scenarios".

Finally, this deliverable establishes the impact assessment methodology, which will occur in three phases: the initial phase consisting in setting the framework (this deliverable), and then performing the impact assessment during each iteration of the PILOTING project: each one corresponding to Deliverable 9.2 and 9.4 respectively.

1.2 Scope of the document

This deliverable provides operational guidelines of the ethical principles and main areas of applicable law in the context of the main technologies that the PILOTING project intends to develop (autonomous vehicles and artificial intelligence) and also with respect to data protection and privacy. This is done in order to provide PILOTING partners with a set of key notions that will serve as a reference to later assess the impact of the work of the project with respect to the relevant ethical and legal issues identified.

1.3 Structure of the document

This deliverable has the following sections:

- Section 1 presents the purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable.
- Section 2 defines the PILOTING Impact Scenarios, in order to identify the SoEL requirements taking into account the different types of pilots and geographical/legal implications.
- Section 3 describes the applicable SoEL principles for data protection and privacy impact, the European and national regulations for the operation of unmanned vehicles and offers a generic view of the applicable regulations for the development of novel technologies such as artificial intelligence.
- Section 4 sets guidelines for the impact assessment for "PILOTING Impact Scenario".

- Section 5 provides details on the impact assessment (IA) methodology to be followed in the PILOTING project in order to determine the activities which require an IA and how will be done the evaluation, treatment, monitoring and review of impacts.
- Section 6 concludes the document with conclusions.

2. Identification of the PILOTING Impact Scenarios

In order to analyze all the relevant principles of data protection (societal), legal and ethics that apply to the project outcomes and activities concerning their impact, this deliverable sets six “PILOTING Impact Scenarios”, which will be a classification of the PILOTING Uses Cases (see deliverable 3.1) differentiating by scenario and type of robotic solution developed (see Table 2).

PILOTING Scenario	PILOTING Use Case	Robot	Type of robotic solution	PILOTING Impact Scenario	Nº
Refineries	Refinery large structures inspection	AEROX	Aerial vehicle (UAV)	Refineries -UAV	1
	Refinery pipes inspection	HYBRID	Hybrid		
	Refinery vessels inspection	BIKE	Crawler	Refineries-Crawler	2
	Refinery ground monitoring	RISING	Ground vehicle (UGV)	Refineries -UGV	3
Bridges/Viaducts	Viaduct visual inspection	AERO-CAM	Aerial vehicle (UAV)	Bridges/viaduct – UAV	4
	Viaduct bearings inspection	VIAD-DRONE	Aerial vehicle (UAV)		
	Viaduct – Sensor installation	VIAD-DRONE	Aerial vehicle (UAV)		
	Viaduct – Surveying targets installation for geometrical precise measurements	VIAD-DRONE	Aerial vehicle (UAV)		
Tunnel	Tunnel local inspection	TT-DRONE	Aerial vehicle (UAV)	Tunnel – UAV	5
	Tunnel general inspection	CART	Ground vehicle (UGV)	Tunnel – UGV	6

Table 2. PILOTING Impact Scenarios.

The objective is to set the “PILOTING Impact Assessment Framework”, taking into account all the legislation related to: the scenario/country where the pilot experiments are to be performed, the type

of robotic solution, the type of technologies to be employed in each one, and the type of data collected by each of them. This framework must involve:

- **Social aspects:** the applicable privacy and data protection framework, taking into account the participation of external participants in project activities (like workshops, demo sessions or surveys) and the use of on-board sensors that can capture data from around. PILOTING partners have made an exhaustive analysis of which on-board sensors in the PILOTING robotic solutions could generate a SoEL issue regarding the possibility of them taking any sensitive external data. They are listed below:
 - **Operational Camara.** A visual camera employs to carry out the inspection, detecting infrastructure defects.
 - **Situational awareness camera.** A visual camera is employed to help the operator/inspector to localize the robot during the inspection process.
 - **Infrared cámara (IR).** An IR camera uses to detect and measure the infrared energy of objects. IR cameras detect these invisible infrared wavelengths, enabling the camera to see in the dark.
 - **LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging).** A remote sensing method that uses light in the form of a pulsed laser to measure ranges (variable distances), and generates a point cloud that makes it possible to distinguish objects.

Table 3. Table 3 shows which of these sensors is on-board each PILOTING robot.

PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camara	Situational awareness camara	Infrared Camara	Lidar
AEROX	X	X		
AERO-CAM	X	X		X
VIAD-DRONE	X	X		
CART	X			X
TT-DRONE	X			
RISING	X		X	X
BIKE	X			X
HYBRID	X			X

Table 3. On-board sensor in each PILOTING robotic solution.

- **Ethical aspects:** Regulatory framework related to novel technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI).
- **Legal aspects:** European legal and regulatory framework related to the use of Unmanned vehicles (UAV and UGV).

From this information, the SoEL requirements, which apply to “PILOTING Impact Scenarios” (Section 3), and Guidelines for the impact assessment (Section 4) have been defined.

3. Identification of the applicable SoEL requirements

This section summarises all the applicable SoEL principles regarding legal, data protection and privacy, and ethics within the PILOTING project.

3.1 Identification of the applicable SoEL principles for the Data Protection and Privacy impact assessment

In WP1 “Ethics requirements” deliverables, it can be found a description of the applicable ethics regulations for data protection and privacy, as well as a description of the procedures followed in PILOTING in relation to these issues: procedures and criteria to identify/recruit research participants, informed consent procedures and how the protection of personal data from external participants will be ensured within the project.

As was concluded in WP1 deliverables, the main applicable regulation for the Data Protection in all PILOTING countries is the “General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)”. WP1 deliverables include a summary of its basic principles.

3.1.1 GDPR definition

The full name of this legislation is Regulation 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing directive 95/46/EC. It is otherwise known as the General Data Protection Regulation, and replaces the previous regime of European data protection law embodied in Directive 95/46/EC. As a Regulation rather than a Directive, it takes force in member states without being transposed into member state law. It took effect as of May 25, 2018.

It is a complex text which aims, on one side, at updating the European legislation on data protection with a legislative act which is more adequate to the modified technological and sociological scenario and, on the other hand, to adopt a text which will be enforceable, without differences, in all the member States. In fact, being the GDPR a regulation, it does not require an implementation by the member States into their national legal framework. As a Regulation rather than a Directive, it takes force in member states without being transposed into member state law.

Regulation no. 2016/679 defines (article 4, par. 1) the personal data as :

“any information Relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or will more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of That natural person”.

Article 4 of the GDPR includes definitions of specific personal data, which are mostly related to sensitive and peculiar aspect of the personality of physical subjects, and notably:

- genetic data: personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person which give unique information about the physiology or the health of that

- natural person and which result, in particular, from an analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question [article 4, n. (13)];
- biometric data: personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioral characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopic data [article 4, n. (14)];
 - data concerning health: personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status [article 4, n. (15)].

Furthermore, processing of personal data being able to reveal racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation are, in general, prohibited and may be processed exclusively in some specific cases. These categories of personal data are subject to additional protections, as they are considered as the hardcore of the protection that must be ensured to citizens by privacy regulations.

Anonymous information is not covered by the EU Regulation. Whereas n. 26 states that "The principles of data protection should therefore not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. This regulation does not therefore concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes".

➤ **Context in which the GDPR applies**

The GDPR applies to the processing of all personal data of individuals residing in EU member states. It does not apply to the processing of personal data "by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties" which specifically includes "the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security and the free movement of such data". Nor does it apply to processing of a purely personal or household activity with no connection to a professional or commercial activity. Finally, it does not apply to processing related to activities outside Union law, including activities concerning national security.

➤ **The main regulatory actors concerned with privacy and data protection.**

Although Regulation 2016/679 is a European legislative initiative, the main regulatory bodies it foresees for the enforcement of data protection law are established at the national level. These take the form of National Data Protection Authorities (sometimes known as 'National Data Protection Commissioners'). Their existence is mandated by the Regulation 2016/679 which requires that each Member State maintain a national institution upon its territory responsible for the oversight of data protection issues. National authorities should, in principle, have the power: of investigation, of intervention, of engagement in legal proceedings, and to hear claims. Although not all national

authorities use these powers effectively. The competent National Data Protection Authority in each PILOTING country has been presented in the deliverable D1.2 “POPD-Requirement N°2”

At the European level exists the European Data Protection Supervisor (the EDPS). The role of the EDPS is to supervise the EU institutions, bodies, offices, and other agencies. The EDPS may therefore be contacted for queries concerning European research projects. While the EDPS has a role in fostering co-operation and consultation between national authorities, it has no powers of oversight or control.

➤ **Data roles**

The main data roles, defined in D1.2- POPD-Requirement N°2, are:

- Controller: “natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law”
- Processor: “a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller”.
- Data Protection Officer: appointed by PILOTING consortium “according to the professional qualities, in particular of the specialized knowledge of the legislation and practices regarding data protection” (art. 37, par. 5 GDPR). This appointment is stated in deliverable D1.2- POPD-Requirement N°2.

Pursuant to article 28 GDPR, ‘Processing by a processor shall be governed by a contract or other legal act under Union or Member State law, that is binding on the processor with regard to the controller and that sets out the subject-matter and duration of the processing, the nature and purpose of the processing, the type of personal data and categories of data subjects and the obligations and rights of the controller’.

The data processor cannot appoint a sub-processor without prior specific or general written authorization of the controller.

Two or more controllers may be considered as joint-controllers where they jointly determine the purposes and means of processing. This last case is quite rare, as the determination of purposes and means is limited to specific data processing activities. In other words, where two subjects collect and manage personal data for a single activity, but they use the data also for other purposes, which are autonomously determined by the subjects themselves, they will be considered joint-controllers only in the first case and not in the latter.

➤ **Principles of data processing**

The architecture of the GDPR is essentially based on 5 principles.

The principles are the following:

- a) Lawfulness, fairness and transparency: transparency is one of the key points in relation to big data. Users are often not fully informed and in the position of properly understanding the privacy policy of the services (e.g. App) which collect their data. The data subject must be, among other things, in a position to easily access the information related to his data, to the data protection officer and to the methods and purposes of the processing. It must also be able to exercise the rights granted to him by the GDPR.
- b) Purpose limitation: the person who collects the data needs to inform the data subject of the purposes for which the data are collected. Subsequently, personal data may be processed only for those purposes and not be used for different purposes.
- c) Data minimization: The data must be relevant and limited to the purposes for which they were collected. Therefore, personal information cannot be collected if they are not closely related to the purposes of collection or, rather, only personal data which are necessary for these purposes can be collected. Thus, the amount of personal data processed must be limited to the minimal amount possible.
- d) Accuracy and updating: the data must be constantly updated and rectified in case of request of the person concerned. In relation to big data, among these rights, the right of cancellation or erasure is specifically important.
- e) Storage limitation: data can only be kept for the time necessary for processing and later destroyed. Personal data can also be stored for longer time periods, insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes.
- f) Integrity and confidentiality: the data controller must ensure adequate security of personal data by appropriate technical and organizational measures, including protection against unauthorized or unlawful processing and against the loss, destruction or accidental damage.

➤ **Legal Basis for the processing of personal data**

Article 6 of the GDPR demands that the processing of personal data must have a legal basis to be lawfully processed. In order to comply with such requirements personal data may be processed for one of the following reasons:

- i. the data subject has unambiguously given his consent; or
- ii. processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract; or
- iii. processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject; or
- iv. processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject; or
- v. processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller or in a third party to whom the data are disclosed; or
- vi. processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by the third party or parties to whom the data are disclosed, except where such interests are overridden by the interests for fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection.

With regards to research within the context of the PILOTING project the informed consent procedures have been defined in deliverable D1.1-H-Requirement N°1.

➤ **Transferring data across borders**

The Data Protection Framework is also important in the regulation of the cross border transfer of data. This is logical given that one of the motivations behind Directive 95/46/EC and the GDPR was to facilitate internal trade that was dependent upon the use of personal data. EU data protection draws a distinction between transfers of data within the EU and transfers of data to third countries i.e. outside the EU.

i. Within the EU

With respect to the GDPR, the general rule regarding the transfer of personal data across national borders is that it is permissible within the EU as the free movement of personal data within the Union cannot be neither restricted nor prohibited.

ii. Outside the EU

For transfers outside the EU, more stringent rules apply. The logic behind this is that countries outside the Union may not have the same level of data protection in their law as the countries of the Union (where GDPR applies).

Article 45 of the GDPR requires a third country to ensure an adequate level of protection as evaluated by the European Commission. If the Commission has decided that the country in question lacks an adequate level of protection, a controller or processor may transfer personal data to a third country only if the controller or processor has provided appropriate safeguards, and on condition that enforceable data subject rights and effective legal remedies for data subjects are available. When neither the country provides adequate safeguards, nor the controller ensures the required safeguards, personal data can be transferred to third countries only if additional conditions are met.

3.1.2 Detailed information on the procedures for data collection and processing. Compliance with national and EU legislation

This section was included as part of the requirements defined in D1.2: POPD - Requirement No. 2 following the guidelines defined in the ethical evaluation report.

At this stage of the project, it is almost impossible to predict precisely at which stages of the project the collected personal data may be processed. However, it is vital to ensure that whenever this happens, any processing will be lawful, as defined by the legislation, and accessed by third parties following the agreement of the data producers. It is also important to emphasize that data will remain secure, and will be accessible at any time only by persons with special permission upon request. The consortium owes, and will comply with the requirements of each partner's national law and EU legislation, to protect individuals in the collection and processing of personal data. The partners of the consortium come from six EU Member States while Switzerland is the only non-EU country that is involved in the project.

<i>Country</i>	<i>Consortium Partner</i>
Spain	CATEC, USE, FERROVIAL, ROBOTNIK
Switzerland	ETHZ, GEIR
France	CHEVRON
Czech Republic	HONEYWELL
Netherlands	APPLUS, QUASSET
Greece	EGNATIA, INLECOM, ICCS
Norway	SINTEF

Table 4. Countries involved in PILOTING project.

Information on national laws is available to the public through the portals of the respective authorities in each country. As it was concluded in deliverable D1.2, and due to the type of data processed in PILOTING, it will not be necessary to require any declaration on compliance and/or authorization under national law for collecting and processing personal data. In addition to national legislation, the consortium will comply with all relevant EU regulations, such as the European Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), which has been in force since 25 May 2018, as mentioned above.

3.1.3 Information on the informed consent procedures with regards to the collection, storage and protection of personal data

This section was included as part of the requirements defined in D1.1: H-Requirement No.1 and D1.2: POPD - Requirement No. 2 following the guidelines defined in the ethical evaluation report.

As was defined in the D1.1: H-Requirement, in case of the collection, transmission, storage and protection of personal data, an informed consent procedure must be defined and implemented. Where required, participants must be asked to sign a form in order to express their consent (see D1.1-Annex II) This form is composed in accordance with legal requirements, including the description of how the data will be used, what type of information will be collected, and what the aim is. The voluntary character of participation will be stated explicitly in the consent form. The informed consent form includes generic details about the project and offers contacts information. It must also inform the participants on their rights with regards to the collection and the usage of their personal data (see Information sheet in D1.1-Annex I).

3.2 European and national legal framework on Unmanned Vehicles

On 11 June 2019 common European rules on drones, Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 & Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947, have been published by the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) to ensure drone operations across Europe are safe and secure. The rules will amongst others help to protect the safety and the privacy of EU citizens while enabling the free circulation of drones and a level playing field within the European Union.

The new rules will replace existing national rules in EU Member States and will be the applicable regulation.

The common rules will help drone operators to have a clear understanding of what is allowed or not and, at the same time, it enables them to operate across borders. Once drone operators have received

an authorization in the state of registration, they are allowed to freely circulate in the European Union. This means that they can operate their drones seamlessly when travelling across the EU or when developing a business involving drones around Europe.

The new rules include technical as well as operational requirements for drones. On one hand they define the capabilities a drone must have to be flown safely. For instance, new drones will have to be individually identifiable, allowing the authorities to trace a particular drone if necessary.

On the other hand the rules cover each operation type, from those not requiring prior authorization, to those involving certified aircraft and operators, as well as minimum remote pilot training requirements.

While the EU regulation was published in June 2019, it will be applicable in July 2020, therefore it will be applicable when experiments or pilot tests are carried out in PILOTING.

While aiming primarily at ensuring safe operations of drones, the European regulatory framework will also facilitate the enforcement of citizen's privacy rights and contribute to address security issues and environmental concerns in the benefit of the EU citizens. It will in addition enable the deployment of an Unmanned Traffic Management System, the U-space, to support the development of drone operations in low-level airspace, beyond visual line of sight and congested areas.

➤ **Categories of operation**

The new framework will introduce three categories of operation (open, specific and certified) according to the level of risks involved. A different regulatory approach will be adopted for each category. Low-risk operations ("open" category) will not require any authorization, but will be subject to strict operational limitations. For medium risk operations, operators will have to require an authorization from the national aviation authority on the basis of a standardized risk assessment or a specific scenario (specific category). Finally, in case of high risk operations, classical aviation rules will apply (certified category).

- Open category

Operations in the open category do not require prior authorizations or pilot license. However, they are limited to operations: in visual line of sight (VLOS), below 120 m altitude and performed with a privately built drone or a drone compliant with the technical requirements defined in the regulation. To demonstrate this compliance drones that can be operated in the open category will bear a class identification label (based on CE marking). Additional operational restrictions apply to each class of drone, in particular with regard to the distance that must be maintained between the drone and non-involved persons.

- Specific category

When the intended operation exceeds the restrictions of the "open" category, the operator should consider operating under the "specific" category (medium risk). Only high-risk operations require compliance to classical aviation rules under the "certified" category (like operating in controlled

airspace). Operations involving drones of more than 25 kg and/or operated beyond visual line of sight will typically fall under the “specific” category.

Before starting an operation in the specific category, operators must either perform a risk assessment (using a standardized method – the SORA – that is provided by EASA) and define mitigation measures or verify that they comply with a specific scenario defined by EASA (or the national aviation authority). On that basis they will be able to obtain an authorization from the national aviation authority (in some cases a simple declaration may be enough). The authorization or the specific scenario will define the authorized operation and the applicable mitigation measures (drone technical requirements, pilot competence, etc.).

- Certified Category

The “certified” category (high risk) includes operations involving large drones in controlled airspaces. Rules applicable to the “certified” category will be the same as for manned aviation: drones must be certified for their airworthiness, pilots shall be licensed, and safety oversight will be performed by the relevant National Aviation Authorities and EASA.

3.3 Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGV)

This section provides a brief summary of the applicable regulation to autonomous road vehicles. It should be noted that land-based robots do not necessarily have to be in the form of what is popularly considered a vehicle that has wheels. As robots for infrastructure inspection and maintenance covered within the PILOTING project will operate in private and off-road settings, many of the regulations concerning autonomous vehicles may not apply.

However, in the absence of legislation that clearly regulates the operation of such vehicles, this section provides an overview of the current safety, regulatory, and legal liability issues concerning autonomous ground vehicles because even if they may not apply to all robots for infrastructure inspection and maintenance, they offer useful guidance and may be helpful in determining the specific measures that need to be developed to regulate and allocate liability for robots that operate in specific commercial domains, and that have not yet been established.

3.3.1 *International regime*

The Convention on Road Traffic, otherwise known as the Vienna Convention on Road Traffic (Vienna Convention), was concluded in 1968 and came into force in 1977. All EU Member States are signatories except Cyprus, Ireland, and Malta. The Vienna Convention requires that ‘every moving vehicle or combination of vehicles shall have a driver’, and a driver is defined as ‘any person who drives a motor vehicle or other vehicle (including a cycle), or who guides cattle, singly or in herds, or flocks, or draught, pack or saddle animals on a road’.

While it was considered relatively detailed and advanced at the time of its drafting, the Vienna Convention was unable to foresee the creation of autonomous vehicles without human drivers facilitated by the ‘jump in technological evolution in parallel with the appearance of new tendencies in the field of motor vehicle improvements’. European states realized this provision was causing them

to lag behind the United States in creating a regulatory environment conducive to developing autonomous cars as the latter is not a signatory. To keep up with technological advances, this provision was amended in 2016 to allow for the use of autonomous vehicles on the roads. The additional changes state:

“Vehicle systems which influence the way vehicles are driven shall be deemed to be in conformity with paragraph 5 of this Article and with paragraph 1 of Article 13, when they are in conformity with the conditions of construction, fitting and utilization according to international legal instruments concerning wheeled vehicles, equipment and parts which can be fitted and/or be used on wheeled vehicles.”

“Vehicle systems which influence the way vehicles are driven and are not in conformity with the aforementioned conditions of construction, fitting and utilization, shall be deemed to be in conformity with paragraph 5 of this Article and with paragraph 1 of Article 13, when such systems can be overridden or switched off by the driver”

Under this new provision, as long as the autonomous vehicle technology meets international standards or if the automated mode can be switched off, autonomous vehicles would be allowed to be driven on public roads of states that are members of the Convention as long as there is a human driver ready to take over.

Though most of the research on autonomous vehicles has been on the carriage of passengers, driverless cars will also be able to be used to transport cargo. In this situation, the Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road (CMR) signed in 1956 may become relevant. The CMR ‘applies to every contract for the carriage of goods by road in vehicles for reward, when the place of taking over of the goods and the place designated for delivery, as specified in the contract, are situated in two different countries, of which at least one is a contracting country, irrespective of the place of residence and the nationality of the parties’. The definition of vehicle in the CMR does not explicitly require human drivers, but it has been argued persuasively that based on an evolutionary interpretation of the CMR, the Convention would be applicable to autonomous vehicles carrying goods internationally.

On the other hand, the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), which includes states in Europe, Asia, and Africa, has been involved in fostering the development of autonomous vehicles since 2014. In June 2019, the UNECE World Forum for Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations, under the leadership of the EU, China, Japan, and the US, issued a framework to guide the future work of the UN on autonomous vehicles. The World Forum’s Working Party on Automated/Autonomous and Connected Vehicles is continuing the work with the establishment of technical groups tasked to explore issues related to autonomous vehicles, including cybersecurity and event data recorders.

The lack of binding regulations on the international level allows for flexibility at the regional and national levels but could also create divergences that would need to be harmonized especially when data generated and collected by robots would inevitably cross national borders. Efforts to harmonize regulations internationally would need to understand and respect the values and principles of the jurisdictions that led to the frameworks and rules they created in order to reach a shared buy-in that would result in consistent implementations and interpretations.

3.3.2 *The EU Position*

Although the EU was late to enter the development of autonomous vehicles, it has since been keeping pace or leading the pack globally. In April 2016, EU Member States signed the Declaration of Amsterdam on cooperation in the field of connected and automated driving, memorializing the EU Commission and the Member States' shared objective of developing autonomous vehicles in the EU.

GEAR 2030, also known as the High Level Group on the Competitiveness and Sustainable Growth of the Automotive Industry in the European Union, drafted a discussion paper for the European Commission detailing the need to create a legal framework for automated vehicles. In October 2017, the High Level Group released its final report on the future of the automotive industry in the EU and the need to foster the development of new technologies with a 'shared strategy on automated and connected vehicles'.

Beyond EU Member States, in March 2017, EEA members Norway, and Switzerland signed a Letter of Intent 'to intensify cooperation on testing of automated road transport in cross border test sites'. In May 2017, the European Commission signalled its commitment to connected and automated mobility as part of a grand plan for European transport. As part of this initiative, the Juncker Commission, in May 2018, reiterated the EU's aim to 'make Europe a world leader in the deployment of connected and automated mobility, making a step-change in Europe in bringing down the number of road fatalities, reducing harmful emissions from transport and reducing congestion' in a communication entitled *On the road to automated mobility: An EU strategy for mobility of the future*.

One of the most instrumental acts by the EU was the overhaul of the approval of vehicles in the EU and combining it with market surveillance in 2018. Vehicles after September 2020 that are certified in one Member State do not need to undergo another certification within the EU. This new approach will allow the EU Commission to harmonize technical standards on safety across the EU, including those relevant to autonomous vehicle technology. While new vehicular technologies such as autonomous cars were already able to go through a certification process prior to the new regulation, this overhaul requires Member States to be consistent in their processes. It has been noted that the increased complexity of the autonomous vehicle technology may lead to growing technical errors, which highlights the need for harmonization of standards.

➤ **Testing**

Testing of autonomous vehicles in Europe has been seen as lagging behind other major markets such as the US and China. This lag has been attributed to the fact that 'Europe emphasizes more on protecting citizens from technological risks'. It was not until the Vienna Convention as amended that autonomous vehicles could be tested on public roads, and even now, unlike in other jurisdictions, there must be a driver in the vehicle during the testing.

Because of the requirement that there be a driver in the vehicle except for a few exceptions such as the UK, Belgium, and the Netherlands, fully autonomous ground robots could not currently be tested on public roads. Manufacturers would need to either design the robots to fit a driver who can take over or limit their testing to private property. Consequently, in most jurisdictions, autonomous ground

vehicles that are meant to operate without humans on board must be tested on private property for the time being, which will comply on all the PILOTING validation experiments.

3.4 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) has become an area of strategic importance and a key driver of economic development. It can bring solutions to many societal challenges but it is essential to join forces in the EU to stay at the forefront of this technological revolution, to ensure competitiveness and to shape the conditions for its development and use (ensuring respect of European values).

In the last two years, the EU has been very active in fostering the development of artificial intelligence. The EU Declaration on Cooperation on AI was signed in April 2018. The Member States agreed to work towards 'a comprehensive and integrated European approach on AI and, where needed, review and modernize national policies to ensure that the opportunities arising from AI are seized and the emerging challenges addressed'. Specifically, the signatories agree to cooperate on 'ensuring an adequate legal and ethical framework, building on EU fundamental rights and values, including privacy and protection of personal data, as well as principles such as transparency and accountability'. The Declaration, a non-binding instrument, has been signed by all EU Member States and Norway.

The European Commission organized a workshop in January 2018 with the European Association for Artificial Intelligence that resulted in a report entitled The European AI Landscape that included country reports from Member States on the AI ecosystem. Communication on AI: Artificial Intelligence for Europe and Coordinated Plan on the Development and Use of Artificial Intelligence Made in Europe were both published by the European Commission in 2018. The former was a response to the European Council's invitation to draft 'a European approach to artificial intelligence' and calls for a 'coordinated approach to make the most of the opportunities offered by AI and to address the new challenges that it brings'. The latter's goals are 'to maximize the impact of investments at EU and national levels, encourage synergies and cooperation across the EU, including on ethics, foster the exchange of best practices and collectively define the way forward'. It encourages Member States to formulate national artificial intelligence strategies and designates the Member States' Group on Digitising European Industry and Artificial Intelligence as the entity to coordinate amongst the Member States and other stakeholders. The European Commission also released Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence in April 2019.

EC President Ursula Gertrud von der Leyen who started her term on 1 December 2019 put artificial intelligence as one her top agenda items and vowed to 'put forward legislation for a coordinated European approach on the human and ethical implications of Artificial Intelligence' within her first 100 days in office.

The High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AIHLEG) formed by the EC and comprising experts from academia, civil society, and industry, released three reports in 2019. Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, published in April 2019, provides a framework for trustworthy AI, which should be lawful, ethical, and robust. Concurrently, it also released the report "A Definition of AI: Main Capabilities and Disciplines", which proposes a definition of artificial intelligence:

Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are software (and possibly also hardware) systems designed by humans that, given a complex goal, act in the physical or digital dimension by perceiving their environment through data acquisition, interpreting the collected structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the knowledge, or processing the information, derived from this data and deciding the best action(s) to take to achieve the given goal. AI systems can either use symbolic rules or learn a numeric model, and they can also adapt their behaviour by analyzing how the environment is affected by their previous actions.

As a scientific discipline, AI includes several approaches and techniques, such as machine learning (of which deep learning and reinforcement learning are specific examples), machine reasoning (which includes planning, scheduling, knowledge representation and reasoning, search, and optimization), and robotics (which includes control, perception, sensors and actuators, as well as the integration of all other techniques into cyber-physical systems).

In June 2019, the AI HLEG also released the Policy and Investment Recommendations for Trustworthy AI containing '33 recommendations that can guide Trustworthy AI towards sustainability, growth and competitiveness, as well as inclusion – while empowering, benefiting and protecting human beings'. A second group created by the European Commission is the European AI Alliance. An online platform, membership is open to all and it allows interested parties to engage in discussions with each other and to communicate with the AI HLEG.

For artificial intelligence to work, algorithms are key. Toward that end, the EC is conducting a study on algorithmic transparency, which is 'an important safeguard for accountability and fairness in decision-making'.

On 19 February 2020, the European Commission published a White Paper aiming to foster a European ecosystem of excellence and trust in AI and a Report on the safety and liability aspects of AI. The White Paper proposes:

- Measures that will streamline research, foster collaboration between Member States and increase investment into AI development and deployment;
- Policy options for a future EU regulatory framework that would determine the types of legal requirements that would apply to relevant actors, with a particular focus on high-risk applications.

After its publication, the White Paper will undergo an open, public consultation process. All European citizens, Member States and relevant stakeholders (including civil society, industry and academics) are invited to participate in the consultation, by answering to a questionnaire.

In addition, Opinion on AI: Artificial Intelligence – The Consequences of Artificial Intelligence on the (Digital) Single Market, Production, Consumption, Employment and Society was published by the European Economic and Social Committee in August 2017 and Artificial Intelligence, Robotics and 'Autonomous Systems' was released by the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies in March 2018, both of which raise important issues related to the development and use of artificial intelligence, including ethics, privacy, and accountability.

On robotics specifically, the European Parliament passed a resolution on Civil Law Rules on Robotics on 16 February 2017 informed by the results of the RoboLaw Project. It requested the Commission to propose definitions of smart robots and autonomous systems, foster scientific research, study necessary legal reform guided by ethical principles, coordinate cooperation amongst Member States, and work on safety standards for safety and security.

Finally, the European Parliament's Legal Affairs Committee also commissioned a report in 2016 entitled European Civil Law Rules in Robotics. The report analyzed the definitions of robots, their possible consciousness, liability issues arising from their use, and an ethical framework for robotics. This report took the approach that artificial intelligence is a key component of robotics technology. Liability issues of artificial intelligence were also addressed by the November 2019 report on Liability for Artificial Intelligence and Other Emerging Technologies drafted by the Expert Group on Liability and New Technologies – New Technologies Formation. The report discusses current civil liability regimes and the challenges that may be faced when attempting to apply them to new technologies. As for liability issues, the fault-based, strict liability, and product liability regimes would all be applicable to robotics technology so long as the elements of the laws are met.

4. Guidelines for the impact assessment

Once the “PILOTING SoEL Impact Assessment Framework” against assessing the project outcomes and activities has been defined, this section provides specific guidelines to complete the impact assessment and ensure the development of the project in a socially, ethically and legally acceptable way.

4.1 Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects

As presented above, the main legislation applicable concerning privacy and data protection framework is the **GDPR**, which applies to all PILOTING countries.

In the framework of the project, there are two potential ways in which data can be collected from external participants:

- **Data collected from participants in project activities.** The project involves the participation of humans in various activities like workshops, surveys or pilot demo sessions.
- **Data capture from the on-board sensors.** In order to set the applicable principles for each impact scenario, the type of data capture by each of the on-board sensors that may pose a SoEL issue (see section 2) has been analyzed:
 - **Operational Camara.** This type of sensor can collect images. In PILOTING will be used for a dual purpose:
 - **Detailed inspection.** The objective is to inspect defects or infrastructure components and its type of lens has been configured for short scope. In this configuration, the camera can only see clearly what is close to the lens and blurs distant objects. Then, even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place, it would not be possible to capture any personal

data. Furthermore, it is important to highlight that this camera will only record the images indicated by the operator/inspector, which will only be focused on the defects to be analyzed.

- **General inspection.** The objective is to inspect the infrastructure and its type of lens has been configured for wide scope. This camera will be used for obtaining a general overview of the structure and to detect possible defects, so it would be able to visualize what is around the infrastructure. However, only images of the infrastructure, previously indicated by the operator/inspector, will be recorded. Then, even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place, any personal data would be collected.
- **Situational awareness camera.** This type of sensor can collect images. However, the situational awareness camera will serve as a support to visually assist the operator/inspector in positioning the robotic vehicle with respect to the infrastructure to be inspected. The image will be focused on the drone components/infrastructure and will not record any type of data.
- **Infrared cámara (IR).** IR cameras detect these invisible infrared wavelengths, enabling the camera to see images in the dark. Nevertheless, if a person is caught by the sensors, these images are not clear enough to identify any sensitive data. In addition, only data from the infrastructure will be analyzed and processed.
- **LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging):** the LIDAR sensor generates a point cloud that allows objects to be identified. However, if a person is detected, it will not be possible to distinguish any personal data (sex, race, etc), because the cloud point generated by this sensor does not have enough resolution. In addition, only data from the infrastructure will be analyzed and processed.

In addition, it is important to highlight that during the pilot experiments, the scenarios will be restricted and no external personnel are expected to enter the area during the missions. Then, it is not expected to collect personal data during the project's technical activities or even in future exploitation activities using PILOTING technologies. However, if personal data are collected, the GDPR must be applied.

Following the GDPR, when personal data will be collected from external participants:

- Informed consent procedures must be defined and implemented.
- The access to the data collected must be restricted only to authorized personnel.
- Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties.
- A Data Project Officer (DPO) must be appointed (which has been already done; see deliverable D1.2, Section 2.4.1).

4.2 Guidelines for the impact assessment in Ethical Aspects

Regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to AI technologies. As was presented in section 3.4, currently, the European Commission is working in a proposal for an AI Regulation, which aims to ensure the protection of fundamental rights and user safety, as well as trust in the development and uptake of AI. Concerning the ethical aspects, the main principles to be

followed (defined so far) has been summarised in the “**Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI**” , which are:

- Respect for human autonomy: Humans interacting with AI systems must be able to keep full and effective self-determination over themselves and be able to partake in the democratic process. AI systems should not unjustifiably subordinate, coerce, deceive, manipulate, condition or herd humans. Instead, they should be designed to augment, complement and empower human cognitive, social and cultural skills. The allocation of functions between humans and AI systems should follow human-centric design principles and leave meaningful opportunities for human choice.
- Prevention of harm: AI systems should neither cause nor exacerbate harm or otherwise adversely affect human beings. This entails the protection of human dignity as well as mental and physical integrity. AI systems and the environments in which they operate must be safe and secure. They must be technically robust and it should be ensured that they are not open to malicious use.
- Fairness: On one hand, ensuring an equal and just distribution of both benefits and costs, and ensuring that individuals and groups are free from unfair bias, discrimination and stigmatization. On the other hand, we must have the ability to contest and seek effective redress against decisions made by AI systems and by the humans operating them. In order to do so, the entity accountable for the decision must be identifiable, and the decision-making processes should be explicable
- Explicability: Explicability is crucial for building and maintaining users’ trust in AI systems. This means that processes need to be transparent, the capabilities and purpose of AI systems openly communicated, and decisions – to the extent possible – explainable to those directly and indirectly affected.

Within PILOTING, an AI system for inspection analytics, which will be integrated in all the PILOTING robotic solutions, will be developed. The idea is to perform inspection data analytics using advanced AI algorithms. These algorithms will be focused only on the detection of infrastructures defects.

4.3 Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspects

The main legal regulation is related to the operation of unmanned vehicles.

➤ UAV

PILOTING project experiments must comply with **European Drone Regulation**. In the PILOTING project, the platforms developed will be within the categories “open” or “specific”, and must always comply with the specifications defined in this regulation (see section 3.2).

Table 5 presents in which category will operate each of the aerial robots developed in PILOTING by scenario.

PILOTING Scenario	Robot	Category
Refineries	AEROX	Specific
	HYBRID	Specific
Bridges/Viaducts	AERO-CAM	Open or Specific
	VIAD-DRONE	Open or Specific
	VIAD-DRONE	Open or Specific
	VIAD-DRONE	Open or Specific
Tunnel	TT-DRONE	N/A

Table 5. UAV within PILOTING.

It is important to point out that the European Drone Regulation does not apply to indoor operations. Then, it does not apply to the tunnel scenario with the TT-DRONE. In this specific case, the only requirements to be fulfilled are the ones related to HSE (Health & Safety Environment).

Then, all the PILOTING flight experiments, except the ones in the tunnel scenario, must comply with:

- The category sets the operational limits, depending on whether it is “open” or “specific”.
- All the required flight authorizations and applicable mitigation measures.

➤ UGV

As was presented in the section 3.3, there is not a specific regulation related to operate autonomous ground vehicles in private properties, as in the case of PILOTING project.

4.4 Guidelines for the impact assessment which applies to each PILOTING Impact Scenario

Table 6 summarises which of the defined SoEL requirements and principles apply to each impact scenario.

Impact Scenarios	Social	Ethical	Legal
Impact Scenario 1: Refinery - UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	UAV regulation
Impact Scenario 2: Refinery -Crawler	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	-
Impact Scenario 3: Refinery- UGV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	-
Impact Scenario 4: Bridge/Viaduct- UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	UAV regulation
Impact Scenario 5: Tunnel - UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	-
Impact Scenario 6: Tunnel -UGV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	-

Table 6. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Scenario.

5. Impact assessment methodology

The primary aim of the PILOTING impact assessment will be to assess potential impacts of the application of the PILOTING project in terms of adherence to the societal, legal and ethical principles outlined in the previous sections.

This deliverable represents the first step in terms of an assessment of whether the principles, key criteria and legal frameworks described will be adhered to by the PILOTING project. In order to do this, it will employ a questionnaire format whereby questions are addressed to each partner in terms of the efforts they have made or will make within the PILOTING project.

Partners of the PILOTING consortium should, to the best of their ability, answer the questions that have been addressed to them, indicating what action they have taken, and where such action has not been taken – to explain why not. The information will be collated and used to make an evaluation report in D9.2 and in D9.4. This report will highlight the efforts that have been made in meeting the criteria in question and where insufficient efforts have been made will call for further efforts (in consultation with the partners concerned).

The requirements, upon which the questionnaires are based, are described below. For the sake of clarity, they have been split into two different sections. These relate to the main areas will be:

1. Requirements related to technical aspects of PILOTING project.
2. Requirements related to project management in PILOTING project.

Please note that the questions listed in each section are for informative purposes and subject to modification prior to being provided to the respective partner.

The general steps of an Impact Assessment are described below together with how such a methodology will be used within work package 9 of the PILOTING project.

5.1 Identification

An important part of the impact assessment is the articulation of a clear and consistent risk identification and statement. The statement is an expression of a relationship between a real, existing event or fact and a potential, unrealized second event or fact. Clear statements help in the identification of possible adverse effects. To help the identification, the assessor should consider the originating source of the risk as it can certify the validity of the risk statement, and it may be helpful in identifying additional risks as well. The last aspect of the process is the identification of the possible outcome and the nature of impact in order to describe the possible consequences. The impact assessment will cover the following main areas: privacy and data protection, unmanned vehicles and novel technologies.

For each of these areas (privacy and data protection, unmanned vehicles and novel technologies) main risks, that will need to be addressed within the context of SoEL aspects of the PILOTING project, will be tackled in terms of the defined requirements. Each of these requirements will represent an obstacle that the PILOTING project will have to overcome or ensure that the benchmark requirements

are met within the context of PILOTING as a project, and also by the deployment of any element created within that project.

To help the identification of risks, the following type of questions will be posed and requested to be answered in D9.2 and in D9.4:

- What are the functionalities and the need for those functionalities as an element of the PILOTING system?
- How do the functionalities of the PILOTING system impact the principles of data protection?
- How do the functionalities of the PILOTING system impact the principles of privacy?
- How do the functionalities of the PILOTING system impact the principles of ethics?
- How do the functionalities of the PILOTING system impact the principles of unmanned vehicles regulation?
- How do the functionalities of the PILOTING system impact the principles of EU approach to AI?

5.2 Analysis

PILOTING is a multidisciplinary project with different work streams, operating within different specialisms and different forms of expertise. Consequently, it is not always possible that all partners that are involved in such projects understand the difference between abstract principles and requirements, and the practical steps needed to secure them. Technical partners that are specialized in processes of technological developments may not have a good understanding of legal principles and likewise, legal or ethical partners may not in reality have the ability to grasp by themselves what is needed in terms of practical and technical steps to actualize those principles. In order to address this issue this impact assessment uses a questionnaire-based approach whereby a series of questions relating to a particular requirement is given to each partner. In doing so, the respective partner is able to describe what exactly has been or will be done to meet a particular requirement as it relates to them. It is only with such specialized feedback from each partner that one can accurately assess whether the requirements that have been posed have been met. It must be noted that the set of posed requirements, as a benchmark, in itself will not guarantee the sufficient outcomes of the assessment.

During the analysis of the identified risks the following type of questions will be posed and requested to be answered in the Impact assessment report regarding each risk:

- What is the likelihood of occurrence of this risk?
- What is the magnitude of the impact should this risk occur?

5.3 Evaluation and treatment

The answers provided by each partner, with their expertise in their specific context within the PILOTING project, will allow an accurate evaluation of whether adequate steps have been taken in terms of meeting the requirements that relate to the risks identified.

Such answers will be used to create an impact assessment report (Deliverable 9.2) that will outline what steps have been taken and whether these are sufficient in order to meet the requirements that has been outlined in the previous section. Where the steps taken have not been sufficient the evaluation report will, through consultation with the relevant partners, outline what further steps may be necessary to ensure that the requirements that are identified are met. Subsequent to the first evaluation report, two periodic reports will be produced at months 12 and 36 (D9.2 and D9.4). These reports will follow the progress made by each partner and affirm that the efforts outlined in the responses to the questionnaire and / or the suggested posed in the present deliverable have been / are being implemented. The following type of questions will help to carry out the review of the progress:

- What mitigating measures have been already implemented or will be implemented to minimize or avoid risks?
- Are there any residual risks left? If yes, are they justified?

6. Conclusions

This deliverable has provided an outline of the ethical principles for the impact assessment related to Social, Ethical and Legal requirements, setting the “PILOTING Impact Assessment Framework”. This is performed in order to provide PILOTING partners with a set of key notions that will serve as a reference to later assess the impact of the work of the project with respect to the relevant issues that have been identified.

Firstly, “PILOTING Impact Scenarios” have been defined in order to complete guidelines for the impact assessment taking into account the differences among different types of pilots and the geographical/legal implications.

After that, the applicable SoEL requirements have been defined, involving the following aspects:

- Social aspects: the main applicable legislation concerning privacy and data protection is the GDPR. This deliverable has outlined the main principles to be applied within the PILOTING project, if necessary. Informed consent procedures must be defined and implemented. The access to the data collected must be restricted only to authorized personnel. Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties. A Data Project Officer (DPO) must be appointed.
- Ethical aspect: Regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the AI technologies, which is summarised in the “**Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI**”, and which are respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability. These principles must be respected in the development of artificial intelligence algorithms.
- Legal aspect: the main legal applicable regulation is related with the operation of UAV: the European Drone regulation. In the PILOTING project, the aerial platforms developed will be within the categories “open” or “specific”, and must always comply with the specifications defined in this regulation. The only exception is the aerial vehicles used in the tunnel scenario where the European Drone regulation does not apply since it is an indoor operation.

Finally, this deliverable sets an impact assessment methodology to be followed within the project (deliverable D9.2 – Impact Assessment Report). This has been structured in three steps:

- Impact assessment Identification: to help the identification of possible risks related to non-compliance with SoEL requirements. To perform this assessment, the PILOTING consortium will employ questionnaires, which will be answered by PILOTING partners.
- Impact assessment analysis: the quantification and qualification will be performed during the analysis of the identified risks.
- Impact assessment evaluation and treatment: A contingency plan will be defined to avoid/minimize each identified risk.

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